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Essay

The Potential Role of Adaptive Management in Environmental Decision Making

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Introduction

Adaptive management is a union of science and management, because theoretical ideas about how better to manage natural resources are tested and proved experimentally, in according to the given real conditions of the ecosystem until we reach optimal decision with minimized impact upon the ecosystems. As Withgott J. (2007. p. 206) justly defines, “adaptive management involves systematically testing different approaches with the aim of improving methods through time”. It also means careful and scrupulous system monitoring the results during the experiment, and adjusting them (or, rather, the best one) to the actual situation. Recognition of the dynamics of the changing and variable natural environment is “one of the basics of the new ecology” (Oglethorpe, 2002, p.2).

Being introduced by Canadian ecologist C. S. Holling in the 1970s, adaptive management, a product of interdisciplinary cooperation between sciences, technology and economics, has become very important trend of the modern environmental science throughout the world. Adaptive management is well suited to managing ecosystems when there is uncertainty regarding how they respond to management actions (Walters, C.J., 1996).

Actually, the role of the adaptive management in Environmental Decision Making become more and more important, as it deals with such a challenging problem as harmonious co-existence of the human and the earth: how best to manage natural resources, how to apply taken decisions upon ecosystems with minimal negative effect, how to maintain conservation of ecosystems with technological progress, thus providing effective dialogue “man-nature”.

1. Structure and principles of adaptive management

Environmental decision making aims finally achieving the sustainable development in managing the ecosystems. This is “designed to reduce environmental impacts and maintain the resource base while allowing a certain amount and type of development” (Marsh 1996). Otherwise, the environmental damage can result in “degrading the resource base on which we ultimately all depend” (Marsh 1996), so that right environmental decisions are extremely important for the existence of the humanity. Adaptive management for the environmental decision making can be achieved by the so-called “learning by doing”, which means a researching the credible evidences to support an optimal reasonable decision (Walters and Holling, 1990). Nowadays, adaptive management techniques are one of the major and most useful tools proposed by environmental decision makers for flexible and responsive management (Gregory et al., 2006).

The complex structure of adaptive management, according to Bennett has several components in its structure includes information, system analysis, plan making, implementation, monitoring and review. As he argues, adaptive management is a “preferred choice of changed management and policy development when the risk of trial-and-error methods is too high and decisions cannot be postponed” (Bennett J. 2005, p. 70), because it allows review the whole process of decision making to achieve the best result, like the iteration process. In the informational step of the adaptive management data is collected, and the on-going research of all the information is being done, to identify knowledge and links. During the system analysis, identifying the process and understanding the relationships and complexity of the system are focused. At the plan making step “resource management goals and targets are established”, and “social, economic and ecological impacts are evaluated to... define a preferred strategy” At the implementation phase agreements to changes are achieved.

Finally, while monitoring and reviewing, it is proved whether management goals and targets are achieved. (Bennett 2005, p.p. 72-74).

As Adger (2009) argues, methodological steps are quite important part of the adaptive management in the process of environmental decision making. Outputs and outcomes of the environmental decision-making must be efficient results for the effective environmental management. Schematic stages and debates, analysis of incomes and outputs are necessary for the environmental decision-making process. Therefore, “participants should be provided with access to information... so as to make the “best” decision given the specific context” (Adger W.N. 2009, p.162). Completeness and accuracy of the information, its analysis, choice of methodology and adaptation towards specific context, and technological tools are necessary parts in the adaptive management.

Important remark about using the adaptive management gives Fennell D when he assumes that ethics needs to be a fundamental concern for adaptive management. “Arriving at a proper (ethical) decision or action requires examining various perspectives and making an informed choice in light of the alternatives and situational circumstances” (Fennell D et al, 2008, p.73). The decisions taken must be weighted carefully, taking into account all the possible consequences and responses that may arise.

2. Types of adaptive management

According to Gregory (2006), two types of adaptive management exist: passive one, which based upon the “developing hypotheses about system..., implementing a management action based on the best available data, and then closely monitoring its effects to test”, and active one, which “involves planned manipulation of the physical environment through testing a range of alternative management actions” (Gregory et al., 2006, p. 435).

While passive adaptive management uses predictive modelling and is completely based upon the knowledge available about this object and problem, active management involves flexible management strategies which may be completely new and must be tested during the experiment. However, in both types of the adaptive management we use adaptation while trying different models of management and testing different decisions.

Adaptation involves changing assumptions and different information obtained through monitoring and project experience. That helps to best understand the system, and to predict possible behaviour and responses which is valuable for the environmental decision making.

Comparing both types of adaptive management it should be noticed that “passive adaptive management is done without controls, it is relatively simple and inexpensive (Prato T. 2005, p.148). On the other hand, lack of controls, replication and randomization causes passive adaptive management to provide unreliable information about ecosystem responses to management actions (Wilhere, G.F., 2002). Therefore active method is more preferable for complex systems.

3. Benefits of adaptive management in environmental decision making

Focusing on the benefits of the adaptive management for the environmental decision making, Newson argues (1992) that it allows considering the future development of the ecosystems more realistically due to many factors and parameters taken into account while choosing the right decision: “the process of planning holds a good many keys to sustainable environmental projection” (1992, p.261). Because of the complicated structure of the ecosystems, their vulnerability towards human impacts on one side, and high pressure of resource-consuming, environment-damaging societies on the other, any projects into

environment “can only cope if this action is planned with care and supported by the best available knowledge” (Newson 1992, p.261).

The fact that the principles of the adaptive management are applicable to any type and scale of ecosystems is very important one, because it is indeed suited both to large and complex ecosystems as well as to smaller ones for assessing risks and scenarios of multiples and changing environmental conditions.

At the adaptive management, knowledge is gained through the feedback mechanism of social learning (cycles of action and reflection); consequently, flexibility to respond to changes is enhanced (Jiggins, J., Roling, N., 2000). As Bennett rightly argued, “adaptive management approach is ideally suited to linking environmental, social and economic systems, and bringing about a fundamental change in the vision of the catchments in which we live” (Bennett J. 2005, p. 71).

When asked about the disadvantages of the adaptive management, first of all the financial side of matter can be mentioned: “because adaptive management programs require some level of monitoring, they can potentially become expensive” (Thom, 2000, p.370), which seems to be true, taking that complex structures are being investigated using different methods, which leads to lot of expenses. Besides, as it is justly said, “even in favourable circumstances adaptive management will not eliminate uncertainties inherent within natural resources management” (National Research Council, 2004, p.3). To some extent, there is a certain level of ambiguity in the adaptive management decision making concept, because in some cases it can be difficult to define “wrong” or “right” decision, which can definitely make the using of adaptive management in environment as not a simple task. However, adaptive management makes a stress upon learning and researching in real conditions what naturally involves some mistakes from experience.

Finally, we would argue that the adaptive management stretches the flexibility and variance of the formalism in the “pure” science, and thus makes it available to compare different scenarios of ecosystem development in case of every kind of human impact. It allows assessing risks and uncertainties, possible responses of ecosystems, and helps to take the optimal decisions, especially in case of large-scale environmental problems, such as global climate change and conservation of biodiversity, where the decisions must be taken very carefully as wrong ones may entail catastrophic consequences.

4. Using the adaptive management in environmental science

Using adaptive management methods is crucial tool for environmental monitoring, because experimentation is central to understanding the ecosystem under adaptive management, enabling learning from both successes and mistakes under a systematic, replicated experimental design (Taylor et al, 1998). Adaptive management techniques and principles may be used in virtually any environmental spatially-oriented task, be it ecosystem restoration, forests reduction analysis, flood or monsoon damage reduction, glacier thawing monitoring, or navigation enhancement. Adaptive management concepts can be therefore applied to solving of different environmental challenging tasks.

For example, adaptive management is a useful instrument for conservation biologists as it allows making decisions in such a complex system, subject to uncertainty, as forest (Wintle B.A. and Lindenmayer D.B., 2008, p.1312). Forests are among the most valuable environments on the Earth and how they are managed is an important factor for the substantial impact on global biodiversity loss. Forest conservation is therefore critical nowadays and is now concerned as a fundamental part of the environmental sustainability.

In coastal ecosystem management using adaptive management is now essential, because there were a lot of failure to achieve goals and good results in this type of

environmental management. The problem here lies in highly complexity and uncertainty of the coastal ecosystem structure: “poor performance has led to a high degree of uncertainty about the potential success of any restoration effort” (Thom, 2000, p.365). Adaptive management helps in making long-term environmental project in coastal ecosystem management, sets goals and targets for multiple scenarios of change, helps in making refine analysis of the situation and prediction modelling (National Research Council, 2001, p.4).

Development of adaptive management strategy can involve several steps, like the followings supposed by the US National Research Council: 1) identification and measurement of ecological indicators 2) design of the monitoring network 3) implementation plan for sampling 4) analysis of the indicators to assess ecosystems response 5) research to support the monitoring and assessment activities.

Conclusion

To conclude, we argue that adaptive management has much to offer for environmental decision making, because, as perfectly Withgott J. claims, “whatever solution we pursue, we must base our decisions on long-term thinking, because to be sustainable, a decision must work in the long term” (Withgott J, 2007. p. 375). And adaptive management plays the most important role in the pursuit of sustainable solutions helping to choose the best decisions in environmental management. It helps managers, environmental policies, GIS–specialists working in the environmental bureaus and organizations to make a quick analysis of an unanticipated events and responses in damaged ecosystems and environment, and to take optimal decision in difficult situations, to modify and improve proposed decisions.

Adaptive management offers important insights into the sustainable governance of natural resources, because the awareness of the importance of good-quality environment requires decision-making management process adaptive to the environmental situation in exact condition and places on the Earth (Oglethorpe, 2002). Therefore, we conclude that adaptive management will play in the nearest future a key and a paramount role in the environmental decision-making for the sustainable development of our world.

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